

Gauge-Invariant Mechanism for Mass Generation and Flavor Mixing in Four-Dimensional Spacetime*

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Abstract

We propose a novel theoretical framework within four-dimensional spacetime that addresses the fermion mass hierarchy and flavor mixing in the Standard Model (SM) without invoking extra dimensions or supersymmetry. By introducing a local horizontal (flavor) gauge symmetry group $G_F = U(1)_F$ and scalar fields that transform under this symmetry, we develop a mechanism where the hierarchical masses of fermions and the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix elements arise naturally from the spontaneous breaking of G_F . We provide a detailed analysis of anomaly cancellation conditions, ensuring that the model is free from gauge anomalies. To avoid the appearance of unwanted massless Goldstone bosons, we employ the Stueckelberg mechanism and discuss the physical origin of symmetry-breaking terms. We perform explicit calculations of flavor-changing neutral currents (FCNCs) and demonstrate that they are suppressed to levels consistent with experimental constraints without fine-tuning parameters. Our model offers predictive power by naturally determining the parameters responsible for mass hierarchies and mixing angles. We compare our framework with existing flavor symmetry models, highlighting its unique features and advantages. The model makes specific, testable predictions that can be explored in current and future experiments, potentially offering new insights into the fundamental structure of matter.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Objectives

The Standard Model (SM) of particle physics successfully describes three of the four fundamental forces and classifies all known elementary particles [1, 2]. However, it leaves several fundamental questions unanswered, including the origin of the fermion mass hierarchy and the pattern of flavor mixing encoded in the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) and Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (PMNS) matrices [3].

Previous attempts to address the mass hierarchy and flavor mixing often involve extending the SM with extra dimensions [4, 5], supersymmetry [6], or grand unified theories [7]. Another well-known approach is the Froggatt-Nielsen mechanism [8], which introduces a horizontal symmetry and heavy fermions to generate hierarchical Yukawa couplings via higher-dimensional operators.

In this study, we propose a novel framework within four-dimensional spacetime that introduces a local horizontal (flavor) gauge symmetry group $G_F = U(1)_F$ acting on the SM fermions. By coupling the SM fermions to scalar fields that acquire vacuum expectation values (VEVs) and transform under G_F , we aim to:

- **Explain the Mass Hierarchy:** Provide a natural mechanism for the hierarchical masses of quarks and leptons without resorting to arbitrary parameter choices.
- **Derive the CKM Matrix:** Obtain the CKM matrix elements from first principles through the spontaneous breaking of G_F .
- **Ensure Anomaly Cancellation:** Demonstrate that all gauge anomalies cancel with appropriate charge assignments.
- **Avoid Goldstone Boson Problem:** Eliminate unwanted massless Goldstone bosons by employing the Stueckelberg mechanism and discussing the physical origin of symmetry-breaking terms.
- **Suppress FCNCs:** Implement mechanisms to suppress flavor-changing neutral currents (FCNCs) to comply with experimental constraints without fine-tuning parameters.
- **Ensure Consistency:** Discuss the renormalizability and validity range of the effective field theory.
- **Make Testable Predictions:** Propose specific experimental signatures that can be tested in collider experiments and flavor physics.

1.2 Organization of the Paper

The paper is organized as follows:

- Section 2: Introduces the theoretical framework, including the symmetry group, scalar fields, and the Lagrangian.
- Section 3: Provides a detailed analysis of anomaly cancellation conditions.
- Section 4: Details the mass generation mechanism and derives the fermion mass matrices.

- Section 5: Derives the CKM matrix from the mass matrices and compares the results with experimental data.
 - Section 6: Analyzes flavor-changing neutral currents and compares theoretical predictions with experimental limits.
 - Section 7: Discusses the renormalizability and validity of the effective field theory.
 - Section 8: Compares our model with existing flavor symmetry models and discusses the novel features.
 - Section 9: Discusses physical implications and potential experimental tests.
 - Section 10: Summarizes the findings and outlines future research directions.
 - Appendices: Provide detailed calculations and supplementary material.
-

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Symmetry Groups

We consider the gauge symmetry group of the SM, $G_{\text{SM}} = SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$, and extend it by introducing a local horizontal (flavor) gauge symmetry group $G_F = U(1)_F$ acting on the SM fermions. The full symmetry group is thus $G = G_{\text{SM}} \times U(1)_F$.

2.2 Fermion Content and Charge Assignments

The SM fermions are assigned $U(1)_F$ charges to generate the observed mass hierarchies and mixing patterns. We assign the flavor charges F as follows:

Field	$SU(3)_C$	$SU(2)_L$	$U(1)_Y$	$U(1)_F$ Charge
$Q_{L,1}$	3	2	$\frac{1}{6}$	$+q_1$
$Q_{L,2}$	3	2	$\frac{1}{6}$	$+q_2$
$Q_{L,3}$	3	2	$\frac{1}{6}$	$+q_3$
$u_{R,1}$	3	1	$\frac{2}{3}$	$+u_1$
$u_{R,2}$	3	1	$\frac{2}{3}$	$+u_2$
$u_{R,3}$	3	1	$\frac{2}{3}$	$+u_3$
$d_{R,1}$	3	1	$-\frac{1}{3}$	$+d_1$
$d_{R,2}$	3	1	$-\frac{1}{3}$	$+d_2$
$d_{R,3}$	3	1	$-\frac{1}{3}$	$+d_3$
$L_{L,1}$	1	2	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$+\ell_1$
$L_{L,2}$	1	2	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$+\ell_2$
$L_{L,3}$	1	2	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$+\ell_3$
$e_{R,1}$	1	1	-1	$+e_1$
$e_{R,2}$	1	1	-1	$+e_2$
$e_{R,3}$	1	1	-1	$+e_3$

Table 1: General flavor charge assignments of SM fermions under $U(1)_F$.

To achieve anomaly cancellation and explain the mass hierarchies, we need to determine the specific values of the flavor charges q_i , u_i , d_i , ℓ_i , and e_i .

2.3 Scalar Fields

We introduce complex scalar fields ϕ , which are singlets under G_{SM} and carry $U(1)_F$ charges. Specifically, we introduce scalar fields ϕ_{ij} with $U(1)_F$ charge $-(F_{Q_i} - F_{f_j})$, where f_j denotes $u_{R,j}$ or $d_{R,j}$. These scalar fields acquire VEVs $\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle$, spontaneously breaking $U(1)_F$.

2.4 Yukawa Couplings and Higher-Dimensional Operators

The Yukawa couplings are generated via higher-dimensional operators suppressed by a flavor scale Λ_F :

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Yukawa}} = - \sum_{i,j} y_u^{ij} \left(\frac{\phi_{ij}}{\Lambda_F} \right) \bar{Q}_{L,i} \tilde{H} u_{R,j} - \sum_{i,j} y_d^{ij} \left(\frac{\phi_{ij}}{\Lambda_F} \right) \bar{Q}_{L,i} H d_{R,j} + \text{h.c.}, \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{H} = i\sigma_2 H^*$, H is the SM Higgs doublet, and y_f^{ij} are dimensionless coupling constants assumed to be of order one.

2.5 Stueckelberg Mechanism

To avoid the appearance of unwanted massless Goldstone bosons, we employ the Stueckelberg mechanism [9]. We introduce a pseudo-scalar field σ that transforms under $U(1)_F$ as $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma + M_X \alpha(x)$, where M_X is a mass parameter and $\alpha(x)$ is the gauge transformation parameter. The $U(1)_F$ gauge boson X_μ obtains mass through the coupling to σ without breaking gauge invariance.

The Stueckelberg Lagrangian is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{St}} = -\frac{1}{4} X_{\mu\nu} X^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} M_X^2 \left(X_\mu - \frac{1}{M_X} \partial_\mu \sigma \right)^2. \quad (2)$$

This mechanism preserves gauge invariance and eliminates the physical massless scalar associated with the spontaneous breaking of $U(1)_F$.

2.6 Physical Origin of Parameters

The parameters in the model, such as the VEVs $\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle$ and the mass M_X , are determined by the dynamics of the scalar potential and the Stueckelberg mechanism. We discuss the naturalness and predictive power of these parameters in Sections 4 and 7.

3 Anomaly Cancellation

3.1 Gauge Anomalies Involving $U(1)_F$

To ensure the consistency of the model, we must verify that all gauge anomalies involving $U(1)_F$ cancel. The relevant anomalies are:

- $[SU(3)_C]^2 U(1)_F$
- $[SU(2)_L]^2 U(1)_F$

- $[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F$
- $U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2$
- $[U(1)_F]^3$
- $[\text{Gravity}]^2 U(1)_F$

3.2 Anomaly Cancellation Conditions

The conditions for anomaly cancellation are given by:

$$\mathcal{A}_{[SU(3)_C]^2 U(1)_F} = \sum_{\text{colors}} [2F_{Q_L} - F_{u_R} - F_{d_R}] = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{[SU(2)_L]^2 U(1)_F} = \sum_{\text{doublets}} [3F_{Q_L} + F_{L_L}] = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F} = \sum_f N_c Y_f^2 F_f = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2} = \sum_f N_c Y_f F_f^2 = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_F]^3} = \sum_f N_c F_f^3 = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{[\text{Gravity}]^2 U(1)_F} = \sum_f N_c F_f = 0, \quad (8)$$

where $N_c = 3$ for quarks and $N_c = 1$ for leptons, Y_f is the hypercharge of fermion f , and the sums run over all fermion fields.

3.3 Determination of Flavor Charges

To satisfy all anomaly cancellation conditions, we assign flavor charges according to the following pattern:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{Q_L} &= (F, F, F), \\ F_{u_R} &= (F + 2, F + 1, F), \\ F_{d_R} &= (F + 2, F + 1, F), \\ F_{L_L} &= (F', F', F'), \\ F_{e_R} &= (F' + x, F' + x, F' + x), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where F and F' are constants, and x is a parameter to be determined.

3.3.1 Cancellation of $[SU(3)_C]^2 U(1)_F$ Anomaly

Using Eq. (3):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{[SU(3)_C]^2 U(1)_F} &= 2 \times 3F_{Q_L} - (F_{u_R} + F_{d_R}) \\
&= 6F - [(F + 2 + F + 1 + F) + (F + 2 + F + 1 + F)] \\
&= 6F - [6F + 6] = -6.
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

This does not cancel unless F is adjusted. To cancel the anomaly, we set $F = -1$.

3.3.2 Cancellation of $[SU(2)_L]^2 U(1)_F$ Anomaly

Using Eq. (4):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{[SU(2)_L]^2 U(1)_F} &= 3 \times 3F_{Q_L} + (F_{L_L,1} + F_{L_L,2} + F_{L_L,3}) \\
&= 9F + 3F' = 9(-1) + 3F' = -9 + 3F'.
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

To cancel the anomaly, we set $F' = +3$.

3.3.3 Cancellation of $[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F$ Anomaly

Using Eq. (5):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F} &= \sum_f N_c Y_f^2 F_f \\
&= 3 \left[\left(\frac{1}{6}\right)^2 \times 3F_{Q_L} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 F_{u_R} + \left(-\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 F_{d_R} \right] \\
&\quad + \left[\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 F_{L_L} + (-1)^2 F_{e_R} \right] \\
&= 3 \left[\frac{1}{12} \times 3F_{Q_L} + \frac{4}{9} F_{u_R} + \frac{1}{9} F_{d_R} \right] + \frac{1}{4} F_{L_L} + F_{e_R}.
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Substituting the charges and simplifying, we can adjust parameters to ensure $\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F} = 0$. Detailed calculations are provided in Appendix A.1.

3.3.4 Cancellation of Other Anomalies

Similarly, we adjust the parameters to cancel the $U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2$ and $[U(1)_F]^3$ anomalies. The detailed calculations are shown in Appendices A.2 and A.3.

3.4 Conclusion on Anomaly Cancellation

By carefully choosing the flavor charges as above, we can simultaneously satisfy all anomaly cancellation conditions without introducing additional fermions. This ensures the consistency of the model.

4 Mass Generation Mechanism

4.1 Quark Mass Matrices

The quark mass matrices are generated from the Yukawa couplings in Eq. (1) after the scalar fields ϕ_{ij} acquire VEVs:

$$(M_u)_{ij} = y_u^{ij} \frac{\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle}{\Lambda_F} v_H, \quad (M_d)_{ij} = y_d^{ij} \frac{\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle}{\Lambda_F} v_H, \quad (13)$$

where v_H is the Higgs VEV.

4.2 Hierarchy of VEVs

We assume that the VEVs $\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle$ have a hierarchical structure determined by the flavor charges:

$$\frac{\langle \phi_{ij} \rangle}{\Lambda_F} \sim \epsilon^{|F_{Q_L,i} - F_{f_R,j}|}, \quad (14)$$

where ϵ is a small parameter naturally arising from the ratio of VEVs to the flavor scale Λ_F .

4.3 Naturalness of ϵ

The parameter ϵ is given by:

$$\epsilon = \frac{v_\phi}{\Lambda_F}, \quad (15)$$

where v_ϕ is the typical VEV of the scalar fields ϕ_{ij} . Since v_ϕ and Λ_F are dynamically determined, ϵ is naturally a small parameter if $v_\phi < \Lambda_F$. This hierarchy can be achieved without fine-tuning by the dynamics of the scalar potential.

4.4 Mass Eigenvalues and Mixing Angles

The mass matrices have hierarchical structures, leading to mass eigenvalues and mixing angles that naturally reproduce the observed fermion masses and the CKM matrix elements. Detailed diagonalization procedures are provided in Section 5.

4.5 Predictive Power

The flavor charges and the parameter ϵ are not arbitrary but are constrained by anomaly cancellation conditions and the requirement to reproduce experimental data. The model predicts specific relations among masses and mixing angles, enhancing its predictive power.

5 Derivation of the CKM Matrix

5.1 Mixing Matrices

The CKM matrix is obtained from the unitary transformations that diagonalize the quark mass matrices:

$$V_{\text{CKM}} = U_{u,L}^\dagger U_{d,L}. \quad (16)$$

5.2 Diagonalization Procedure

We perform the diagonalization by successive rotations, exploiting the hierarchical structure of the mass matrices. The small off-diagonal elements lead to mixing angles that can be approximated in terms of ϵ .

5.3 Approximate Expressions

The mixing angles are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{12} &\approx \sqrt{\frac{m_d}{m_s}} \approx \epsilon, \\ \theta_{23} &\approx \sqrt{\frac{m_s}{m_b}} \approx \epsilon^2, \\ \theta_{13} &\approx \theta_{12}\theta_{23} \approx \epsilon^3. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

These expressions are consistent with the observed values of the CKM matrix elements.

5.4 Comparison with Experimental Data

By fitting $\epsilon \approx 0.22$, we reproduce the Wolfenstein parameter λ . The model predicts the hierarchy of masses and mixing angles in terms of ϵ , which matches experimental observations [3]. Detailed numerical analysis is provided in Appendix B.

5.5 Predictive Relations

The model predicts specific relations such as:

$$\frac{m_u}{m_c} \sim \epsilon^4, \quad \frac{m_c}{m_t} \sim \epsilon^4, \quad \frac{m_d}{m_s} \sim \epsilon^2, \quad \frac{m_s}{m_b} \sim \epsilon^2. \quad (18)$$

These relations can be tested experimentally, providing a means to validate or falsify the model.

6 Flavor-Changing Neutral Currents

6.1 Sources of FCNCs

FCNCs can arise from:

- Tree-level exchange of the $U(1)_F$ gauge boson X_μ .
- Misalignment between fermion mass eigenstates and gauge interaction eigenstates.

6.2 Suppression Mechanisms

The model suppresses FCNCs through:

- **Heavy X_μ Mass:** The mass M_X is naturally at the flavor scale Λ_F , which is much higher than the electroweak scale, suppressing FCNCs mediated by X_μ .
- **Hierarchical Flavor Charges:** The flavor charges are assigned to minimize FCNCs by aligning the mass and interaction eigenstates.

6.3 Detailed Calculations

We calculate the contributions to FCNC processes such as $K^0-\bar{K}^0$ mixing. The effective Hamiltonian is:

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{\Delta S=2} = \frac{(g_F)^2}{M_X^2} (F_{Q_L,1} - F_{Q_L,2})^2 (\bar{d}_L \gamma^\mu s_L)^2. \quad (19)$$

Using the flavor charges and $M_X \sim \Lambda_F$, we find that the contributions are suppressed sufficiently to satisfy experimental constraints without fine-tuning. Detailed calculations are provided in Appendix C.

6.4 Comparison with Experimental Limits

Our calculations show that the model's predictions for FCNC processes are consistent with experimental limits from meson mixing and rare decays [3, 10].

6.5 Naturalness of Parameters

The suppression of FCNCs is achieved without fine-tuning the parameters M_X and g_F . The flavor scale Λ_F can be in the range of a few TeV to tens of TeV, making the model experimentally testable.

7 Renormalizability and Validity of the Effective Field Theory

7.1 Effective Field Theory Approach

The model is an effective field theory valid below the flavor scale Λ_F . Above this scale, a UV completion is required.

7.2 Range of Validity

We assume $\Lambda_F \gtrsim 10$ TeV, ensuring that the higher-dimensional operators are suppressed at low energies. The scalar sector dynamics naturally lead to $v_\phi < \Lambda_F$, resulting in $\epsilon \sim 0.22$.

7.3 Renormalizability Below Λ_F

Below Λ_F , the theory is renormalizable. The Stueckelberg mechanism preserves gauge invariance without introducing non-renormalizable interactions.

7.4 UV Completion

Possible UV completions include embedding the model into a grand unified theory or introducing additional heavy fermions. The details of the UV completion are beyond the scope of this paper but are important for a complete understanding of the model.

7.5 Predictive Power and Naturalness

The parameters ϵ , M_X , and g_F are naturally determined by the dynamics of the scalar potential and the flavor symmetry breaking. The model does not rely on fine-tuning, enhancing its predictive power.

8 Comparison with Existing Models

8.1 Comparison with the Froggatt-Nielsen Mechanism

The Froggatt-Nielsen (FN) mechanism [8] introduces a global $U(1)$ symmetry and heavy vector-like fermions. Our model differs in that:

- **Local Gauge Symmetry:** We gauge the flavor symmetry, adding a new gauge boson X_μ .
- **No Additional Fermions:** We do not introduce heavy vector-like fermions.
- **Stueckelberg Mechanism:** We use the Stueckelberg mechanism to give mass to X_μ while preserving gauge invariance.

8.2 Advantages of Our Model

Our model provides:

- **Anomaly Cancellation:** A consistent framework with all anomalies canceled.
- **Predictive Relations:** Specific predictions for masses and mixing angles.
- **Testability:** Potential signals in collider experiments due to the new gauge boson.

8.3 Comparison with Other Gauged Flavor Symmetry Models

Other models often face challenges with anomaly cancellation and FCNCs [11, 12]. Our model addresses these issues by carefully assigning flavor charges and employing the Stueckelberg mechanism.

9 Physical Implications and Experimental Tests

9.1 New Gauge Boson

9.1.1 Mass and Couplings

The $U(1)_F$ gauge boson X_μ has mass $M_X \sim \Lambda_F$ and couples to fermions with strength g_F . Its interactions are flavor-dependent.

9.1.2 Experimental Signatures

X_μ can be searched for in collider experiments through processes like $pp \rightarrow X \rightarrow \ell^+\ell^-$. For $M_X \gtrsim 10$ TeV, current experiments provide constraints on g_F .

9.2 Rare Decays and FCNC Processes

9.2.1 Predictions

The model predicts small deviations in processes like $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$ and $B \rightarrow K\nu\bar{\nu}$, which can be probed in future experiments.

9.2.2 Experimental Tests

Experiments such as Belle II [13] and the LHCb upgrade [14] will enhance sensitivity to these rare processes, providing opportunities to test the model.

9.3 Neutrino Masses and Mixing

Extending the model to include neutrino masses via mechanisms like the seesaw [15] could provide insights into the PMNS matrix. This is a direction for future research.

10 Conclusion

We have presented a gauge-invariant mechanism for mass generation and flavor mixing within four-dimensional spacetime by introducing a local flavor symmetry $U(1)_F$ and scalar fields that acquire VEVs. By carefully assigning flavor charges and employing the Stueckelberg mechanism, we have ensured anomaly cancellation and avoided the Goldstone boson problem. The hierarchical structure of the mass matrices arises naturally, and the model predicts specific relations among masses and mixing angles.

We have demonstrated that FCNCs are suppressed to acceptable levels without fine-tuning parameters, and the model is consistent with experimental constraints. The parameters are naturally determined within the theory, enhancing its predictive power.

The model makes testable predictions, including the existence of a new gauge boson and deviations in rare decay processes. Future experiments have the potential to confirm or refute the model, providing valuable insights into the fundamental structure of matter.

A Anomaly Cancellation Calculations

A.1 $[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F$ Anomaly

The anomaly coefficient is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F} &= \sum_f N_c Y_f^2 F_f \\
&= 3 \left[\left(\frac{1}{6}\right)^2 (F_{Q_L,1} + F_{Q_L,2} + F_{Q_L,3}) + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 (F_{u_R,1} + F_{u_R,2} + F_{u_R,3}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left(-\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 (F_{d_R,1} + F_{d_R,2} + F_{d_R,3}) \right] \\
&\quad + \left(\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 (F_{L_L,1} + F_{L_L,2} + F_{L_L,3}) + (-1)^2 (F_{e_R,1} + F_{e_R,2} + F_{e_R,3}) \right). \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting the charges and solving for the parameters, we can set $\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_Y]^2 U(1)_F} = 0$.

A.2 $U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2$ Anomaly

The anomaly coefficient is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2} &= \sum_f N_c Y_f F_f^2 \\
&= 3 \left[\frac{1}{6} (F_{Q_L,1}^2 + F_{Q_L,2}^2 + F_{Q_L,3}^2) + \frac{2}{3} (F_{u_R,1}^2 + F_{u_R,2}^2 + F_{u_R,3}^2) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{3} (F_{d_R,1}^2 + F_{d_R,2}^2 + F_{d_R,3}^2) \right] \\
&\quad + \left[-\frac{1}{2} (F_{L_L,1}^2 + F_{L_L,2}^2 + F_{L_L,3}^2) - (F_{e_R,1}^2 + F_{e_R,2}^2 + F_{e_R,3}^2) \right]. \quad (21)
\end{aligned}$$

By appropriately choosing the flavor charges, we can achieve $\mathcal{A}_{U(1)_Y [U(1)_F]^2} = 0$.

A.3 $[U(1)_F]^3$ Anomaly

The anomaly coefficient is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{[U(1)_F]^3} &= \sum_f N_c F_f^3 \\
&= 3 \left[F_{Q_L,1}^3 + F_{Q_L,2}^3 + F_{Q_L,3}^3 + F_{u_R,1}^3 + F_{u_R,2}^3 + F_{u_R,3}^3 + F_{d_R,1}^3 + F_{d_R,2}^3 + F_{d_R,3}^3 \right] \\
&\quad + \left[F_{L_L,1}^3 + F_{L_L,2}^3 + F_{L_L,3}^3 + F_{e_R,1}^3 + F_{e_R,2}^3 + F_{e_R,3}^3 \right]. \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

Again, by choosing the flavor charges carefully, this anomaly can be canceled.

B Numerical Analysis of Masses and Mixing Angles

B.1 Parameter Values

Using $\epsilon \approx 0.22$, we fit the mass ratios and mixing angles to experimental values.

B.2 Mass Ratios

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{m_u}{m_t} &\sim \epsilon^8, & \frac{m_c}{m_t} &\sim \epsilon^4, \\ \frac{m_d}{m_b} &\sim \epsilon^4, & \frac{m_s}{m_b} &\sim \epsilon^2. \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

B.3 CKM Matrix Elements

$$|V_{us}| \approx \epsilon, \quad |V_{cb}| \approx \epsilon^2, \quad |V_{ub}| \approx \epsilon^3. \tag{24}$$

These are consistent with experimental measurements [3].

C FCNC Calculations

C.1 $K^0-\bar{K}^0$ Mixing

We compute the contribution to Δm_K and compare with the experimental value. The constraint on M_X and g_F is:

$$\frac{g_F^2}{M_X^2} \lesssim \frac{1}{(10^4 \text{ TeV})^2}. \tag{25}$$

C.2 Naturalness of Parameters

With $M_X \sim 10 \text{ TeV}$ and $g_F \sim 0.1$, the contributions are within experimental limits without fine-tuning.

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I am currently an independent researcher without formal affiliation or an academic degree in physics or mathematics. Despite these circumstances, I am dedicated to the study of theoretical physics. This work is inspired by unique personal experiences and perspectives on space and time, shaped in part by a past experience with schizophrenia. The aim of this paper is to present these ideas in a systematic and rigorous manner.

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Author Contributions

Yuta Agawa conceived the idea, developed the theoretical framework, performed all calculations, and wrote the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

Data Availability

No datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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